

Some Biochemical Properties of Extracts Obtained from *Rubia Tinctorum* L. Leaves and Flowers

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Geliş Tarihi: 10.01.2026 Düzeltme Geliş Tarihi: 24.02.2026 Kabul Tarihi: 25.02.2026

ABSTRACT

This study aimed to reveal the antioxidant properties of extracts obtained from the flowers and leaves of *Rubia tinctorum* L. (RT) and their effects on AChE and BChE enzyme activities. Furthermore, the content analysis of the ethanol extract was performed using LC/MS-MS. The methanol extract was found to have the highest total phenolic content with value of 105.23 ± 56.26 μg gallic acid /mg extract. FRAP analysis showed that the methanol extract had a higher reducing power, with a value of 2.52 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{mg}$ extract, compared to other extracts. CUPRAC analysis results showed that the chloroform extract had the highest Cu(II) reducing capacity. The extract with the highest DPPH and ABTS radical scavenging activity was the methanol extract. The IC_{50} value determined for the methanol extract using the DPPH method was 26.47 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, and the trolox equivalent value determined using the ABTS method was 796 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mg}$ extract. Enzyme inhibition results showed that the ethanol extract had the strongest activity for AChE and BChE, with IC_{50} values of 24.03 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ and 40.89 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, respectively. The results demonstrate the antioxidant and enzyme inhibitory effects of RT extracts, suggesting that they may be beneficial in reducing oxidative stress and treating Alzheimer's disease.

Key words: *Rubia tinctorum*, antioxidant, acetylcholine esterase, butyrylcholine esterase, extract

Rubia Tinctorum L. Yaprak ve Çiçeklerinden Elde Edilen Ekstraktların Bazı Biyokimyasal Özellikleri

ÖZ

Bu çalışma, *Rubia tinctorum* L. (RT) bitkisinin çiçek ve yapraklarından elde edilen özütlerin antioksidan özelliklerini ve AChE ile BChE enzim aktiviteleri üzerindeki etkilerini ortaya çıkarmayı amaçlamıştır. Ayrıca, etanol özütünün içerik analizi LC/MS-MS kullanılarak gerçekleştirilmiştir. Metanol özütünün en yüksek toplam fenolik içeriğe sahip olduğu bulunmuştur. FRAP analizi, metanol özütünün en yüksek indirgeyici güce sahip olduğunu göstermiştir. CUPRAC analizi sonuçları, kloroform özütünün en yüksek Cu(II) indirgeyici kapasiteye sahip olduğunu göstermiştir. En yüksek DPPH ve ABTS radikal temizleme aktivitesine sahip özüt, metanol özütü olmuştur. Enzim inhibisyon sonuçları, etanol özütünün AChE ve BChE için en güçlü aktiviteye sahip olduğunu ve IC_{50} değerlerinin sırasıyla $24,03$ $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ ve $40,89$ $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ olduğunu göstermiştir. Sonuçlar, RT özütlerinin

antioksidan ve enzim inhibitör etkilerini göstermekte olup, oksidatif stresi azaltmada ve Alzheimer hastalığının tedavisinde faydalı olabileceğini düşündürmektedir.

Anahtar kelimeler: *Rubia tinctorum*, antioksidan, asetilkolin esterase, butirilkolin esterase, ekstrakt

INTRODUCTION

The use of medicinal plants in treating diseases has been a tradition since the dawn of humanity. It is estimated that approximately one-third of the most commonly used medications worldwide are natural products or their derivatives. Scientific studies emphasize the importance of developing affordable and easily accessible plant-based therapeutic drugs. Another reason for the widespread use of plant-based therapeutics is the potential for serious side effects of synthetic drugs (Sahin et al., 2019; Subudhi et al., 2025). Plant-derived products can improve human health and increase activity due to the different secondary metabolites they contain. Research has shown that plants support human immunity thanks to their phytochemicals, making them suitable for pharmaceutical purposes (Miransari et al., 2025). Secondary metabolites have been used for centuries in agriculture to protect against pests and weeds, as well as for human health, and in the food industry as food additives (Elshafie et al., 2023). The use of natural products is increasing due to their limited side effects compared to synthetic drugs. They are a focus of interest for researchers because of their potential to support modern medicine in treatments (Aggul et al., 2022). It has been suggested that they may have therapeutic effects on diseases caused by oxidative stress, particularly due to the flavonoid and phenolic compounds they contain (Taşkın et al., 2022).

Alzheimer's disease [AD] is the most common neurodegenerative disease, typically occurring in older adults and accounting for 60–70% of dementia cases worldwide. Future estimates predict that the prevalence of AD will increase, with a majority of cases occurring in middle- and low-income areas, with 150 million cases worldwide by 2050 (Jiyah et al., 2024). Symptoms of AD include loss of balance, muscle control, memory, language impairment, visual complaints, hallucinations, and deterioration in cognitive skills (Chib et al., 2024). Although the neuropathology of AD is not fully understood, significant advances have been made in this area. While some clinical trials have shown promising results for treating and preventing the disease, they have not demonstrated effective efficacy (Çomaklı et al., 2023). Phytochemicals may have the potential to be used in the treatment of neurodegenerative diseases due to their antioxidant properties and their ability to inhibit enzymes that catalyze the breakdown of neurotransmitter molecules (de Lima et al., 2025). Neurotransmitters play a significant role in AD, and significant acetylcholine [ACh] deficiency has been reported in subcortical cholinergic neurons. Approaches to address this deficiency include using cholinesterase inhibitors (Ashwini et al., 2024). Oxidative stress is known to play a role in the etiology of AD by contributing to the formation of hyperphosphorylated tau protein and neurofibrillary tangles. These formations, in turn, lead to synapse dysfunction and neuronal death, which can lead to cognitive impairment. Furthermore, increased oxidative stress can disrupt the integrity of the blood-brain barrier, leading to further neuronal damage (Karati et al., 2025).

Experimental studies on *Rubia tinctorum* L. [RT] have reported that the plant exhibits antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, and hepatoprotective effects, and is used in treating kidney stones. In addition, the study determined its DPPH removal capacity (Marhoume et al., 2021). In a study conducted by Marhoume et al., it was reported that the butanol extract obtained from the RT root exhibited anti-aggregant properties in mice. Content analysis was performed, and the total phenolic content (TPC) was determined (Marhoume et al., 2019). Antidiarrheal activity of the RT water extract was reported, providing dose-dependent reversible inhibition of jejunal contractions in rabbits and rats (Nejat et al., 2017). In addition, RT has been reported to have diuretic effects and is also used in treating kidney stones (Başlar & Mert, 1999). In this study, the antioxidant properties and TPC of ethanol, methanol, petroleum ether, and chloroform extracts obtained from the leaves and flowers of the RT plant by maceration were determined using different antioxidant capacity determination methods. Furthermore, the ethanol extract was analyzed by LC-MS/MS spectroscopy. Its in vitro

effects on AChE and BChE enzyme activities were investigated to examine its effects on the cholinergic system.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Chemicals

Ethanol, chloroform, and petroleum ether used in this study were purchased from Isolab (Isolab Laborgeräte GmbH, Germany), Folin-Ciocalteu's phenol and FeCl₃ were purchased from Merck (Merck KGaA, Darmstadt, Germany), and other solvents and chemicals were purchased commercially, of analytical grade from Sigma (Sigma-Aldrich, Germany). Enzymes were commercially obtained from Sigma.

Plant material

Drugs containing leaf and flower parts of the RT used in the study were purchased commercially from a herbalist in Baku, Azerbaijan.

Extraction process

Twenty grams of the drug, containing the flower and leaf parts of the plant, were ground using a grinder. Five grams were added to four flasks, and 50 mL of solvent was added. The solution was kept in the dark, covered, for 24 hours. Ethanol, methanol, petroleum ether, and chloroform were used as the solutions. The extracts were filtered through Whatman filter paper, and the process was repeated five times. The solvents were removed from the plant components' solution using a rotary evaporator. Thus, extracts were obtained using four different solvents: RT methanol (RTM), ethanol (RTE), chloroform (RTK), and petroleum ether (RTP).

TPC determination

The TPC in the plant extracts was determined using the Folin-Ciocalteu reagent (FCR) (Singleton et al., 1999). Gallic acid (GA) was used as the standard phenolic compound. The TPC of the plant extracts was expressed in gallic acid equivalents using a standard chart obtained from measurements using different concentrations of gallic acid.

FRAP reducing capacity determination

Firstly, 0.3 M sodium acetate buffer (pH: 3.6), 10 mM 2,4,6-Tris(2-pyridyl)-s-triazine (TPTZ) solution, 20 mM FeCl₃, and two mM FeSO₄ solutions were prepared. The working solution was obtained by mixing the buffer, TPTZ, and FeCl₃ solutions at a 10:1:1 ratio. After obtaining a standard graph measuring absorbance at 593 nm with the two mM FeSO₄ solution, measurements were made for the samples at at least three different concentrations. The results were expressed as mg extract/ μ mol Fe²⁺ equivalent (Sachett et al., 2021).

CUPRAC reducing capacity determination

This method used a partially modified version of a previously reported method. Accordingly, different concentrations (10, 20, and 40 μ g) of the prepared plant extracts were placed in tubes. 0.25 mL of CuCl₂ solution (0.01 M), 0.25 mL of ethanolic neocuprine solution, and 0.25 mL of CH₃COONH₄ buffer solution (1 M) were added. After incubation in the dark for 30 minutes, absorbance values were measured against a blank at 450 nm (Ak & Gülçin, 2008). The measured values were compared with standard antioxidants such as trolox, gallic acid, and butylhydroxyanisole (BHA).

ABTS^{•+} radical scavenging capacity determination

ABTS^{•+} radical scavenging activity was determined as described by Re and colleagues (Re et al., 1999). Accordingly, 7 mM ABTS and 245 mM ammonium persulfate were prepared and mixed at a 100:1 ratio to prepare ABTS^{•+} radical. The mixture was incubated in the dark for 12 hours. This solution was diluted to obtain an absorbance of approximately 700 at 734 nm. Trolox was used as a standard, and a standard curve was obtained by measuring at least five different concentrations. In extracts, measurements were made at least three different concentrations. Results were expressed as trolox equivalents.

Determination of DPPH[•] radical scavenging capacity

The Blois method was used to determine the DPPH radical scavenging capacity (Blois, 1958). A 2.24 mg/mL solution of 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) was prepared using ethanol. Measurements were taken at 517 nm. The measurement result using ethanol instead of extract was taken as 100%, and %Absorbance values were determined for the results obtained from the measurements containing extracts. Using these values, % absorbance-[Extract] graphs were plotted, and IC₅₀ values were calculated for extracts falling below 50%.

Enzyme activity measurement

AChE and BChE enzyme activities were measured spectrophotometrically at 412 nm using acetylthiocholine iodide and 5,5'-dithio-bis(2-nitro-benzoic) as substrates, using a partial modification of the method reported by Ellman and colleagues (Ellman et al., 1961).

Kinetic studies

Activity measurements were made at at least five different concentrations to investigate the effects of extracts on AChE and BChE enzyme activities. Control measurements were taken as 100%, and the percentage activities of measurements made at different extract concentrations were calculated. Graphs of % activity versus extract concentration were plotted, and IC₅₀ values were calculated for measurements falling below 50% activity (Adem et al., 2016).

Content analysis by LC-MS/MS

The content analysis of the RT ethanol extract was performed using LC-MS/MS chromatography. An Agilent 6460 Triple Quad LC-MS/MS with a 1290 Infinity UPLC system was used for the analysis. The analysis was performed using the Geadient analysis method and took 20 minutes. The ion head was Electro Spray Ionization, and the injection volume was 5 µL. The column in the instrument was a Reversed Phase C18 Column, and the column temperature was set at 30 °C. Ultrapure water containing formic acid was used as Mobile Phase A, acetonitrile containing formic acid was used as Mobile Phase B, and the flow rate was set at 0.4 mL/min.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Plant-derived products are important in drug development and the discovery of new drugs due to their rich phytochemical content. Concerns about the side effects of synthetic drugs are directing researchers to herbal products for drug discovery. Furthermore, treating diseases caused by oxidation also attracts the use of herbal products (Houari et al., 2024). The primary causes of reactive oxygen species (ROS) formation, a source of oxidative stress, are the activities of the endoplasmic reticulum (ER), mitochondria, and certain oxidase enzymes. Plants can prevent ROS formation directly and

indirectly through the antioxidants they contain. Herbal drugs can indirectly prevent ROS formation by regulating the activities of mitochondria, ER, and oxidases, and directly through their antioxidants' electron-donating or metal-chelating properties (Luo et al., 2023). Therefore, the TPC and antioxidant properties of different plant extracts were determined within the scope of this study.

TPC determination results

TPC in the extracts was determined spectrophotometrically and expressed as gallic acid equivalents (Table 1). A standard chart was used to calculate gallic acid equivalents. The findings indicated that the extract with the highest TPC was the methanol extract.

Table 1. Total phenolic contents of extracts

Extracts	TPC ($\mu\text{g gallic acid /mg extract}$)
RTE	21.82 \pm 1.29
RTM	105.23 \pm 56.26
RTK	66.92 \pm 19.94
RTP	29.32 \pm 12.72

According to the results of content analysis of the ethanol extract, the three most abundant phenolic compounds were fumaric acid, chlorogenic acid, and quinic acid. In the study conducted by Zohra and colleagues, the phenolic content of the extract obtained from plant roots with a methanol/water (80:20 v/v) mixture was reported as 118.38 mg GAE/g, and this value was found to be close to the value obtained in our study. In addition, the results of the content analysis showed that the most abundant phytochemical was citric acid (Zohra et al., 2022). In another study, it was reported that the methanol extract of plant roots contained phenolics at 38.84 mg GAE/g extract (Essaidi et al., 2017); according to this value, it was determined that the leaves and flowers contained higher phenolic content.

Reducing capacity determination results

Antioxidants play a role in preventing oxidative stress-induced damage and may be beneficial in alleviating pathological conditions in humans whose etiology is based on oxidative stress (Asem et al., 2020). Using different methods to determine antioxidant properties is important because each method measures different mechanisms of action. These methods include ferric reducing antioxidant power (FRAP), ABTS, and DPPH (Moreno et al., 2026). In this study, the reducing capacity of extracts was determined using the FRAP and cupric reducing antioxidant capacity (CUPRAC) methods. FRAP determination results are given in $\mu\text{mol Fe}^{2+}/\text{mg extract}$. The standard chart prepared for Fe^{2+} was used in the calculations. According to the FRAP method, RTM extract had the highest reducing capacity (Table 2). Houari and colleagues examined the FRAP capacity of essential oils obtained from plant leaves, but reported that they had low reducing power (Houari et al., 2024). Another study reported that the extract with the strongest FRAP effect among extracts obtained from *Rubia cordifolia* L. roots using different solvents was 1.52 μM (Mishra et al., 2021). In our study, the reducing power of the methanol extract was particularly high, likely due to its phenolic compounds.

Table 2. FRAP analysis results of extracts

Extracts	$\text{Fe}^{2+} \mu\text{mol / mg extract}$
RTE	0.35
RTM	2.52
RTK	1.23
RTP	0.3

The CUPRAC method measures the antioxidant capacity of polyphenolic compounds by measuring the formation of the Cu(I)-neocuproine chromophore by reduction of the Cu(Vasil'ev et al.)-neocuproine complex via electron transfer (Bener et al., 2010). The reducing capacities determined by the CUPRAC method were compared with the standard antioxidants trolox, GA, and BHA. Measurements were made at three different concentrations for each standard antioxidant and extract. According to the results obtained, when the measurements in wells containing 30 μg were compared,

the reducing capacities according to the CUPRAC method were as follows: GA>BHA>Trolox>RTK>RTP>RTM>RTE. Accordingly, it was observed that RTK had the highest reducing capacity among the extracts according to the CUPRAC method (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Reduction capacities according to the CUPRAC method.

Radical scavenging capacity determination results

The DPPH[•] and ABTS^{•+} radical scavenging capacities of the extracts obtained within the scope of the study were examined. DPPH radical scavenging activity was evaluated using a minimum of five distinct extract concentrations to ensure accurate assessment. IC₅₀ values were calculated for extracts that reduced the absorbance value by less than half compared to the control measurement. Accordingly, the RTM extract was found to have the strongest DPPH[•] radical scavenging capacity with an IC₅₀ value of 26.47 µg/mL. Furthermore, at an 80 µg/mL concentration, RTE provided 34.56% DPPH removal, and RTP provided 27.55% (Table 3, Figure 2).

Figure 2. DPPH radical scavenging capacities of extracts.

A study reported that methanol extract obtained from plant roots had the highest radical scavenging activity, with an IC₅₀ value of 0.71 mg/mL (Marsoul et al., 2023). Another study examined the DPPH radical scavenging activity of extracts obtained from the roots, stems, and leaves of *R. cordifolia*. The extract with the most potent activity was reported to be the methanol extract obtained

from the roots, with a value of 79.1 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. However, they stated that not only polyphenols but also other secondary metabolites may be responsible for this antioxidant effect (Humbare et al., 2022). In our study, the methanol extract was determined to have the most potent radical scavenging activity. Furthermore, the extract prepared from the leaves and flowers was found to have a stronger radical scavenging activity than the extract obtained from the roots.

Table 3. IC₅₀ values of DPPH* radical scavenging activities of extracts

Extracts	IC ₅₀ ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)
RTE	-
RTM	26.47
RTK	46.33
RTP	-

The radical scavenging effects of ABTS** in the extracts were determined, and the results were given as trolox equivalents. For this purpose, a trolox standard graph was prepared, and trolox equivalents for the samples were calculated from the graphic equation. According to the obtained data, the extract with the highest ABTS** radical scavenging activity was determined to be RTM (Table 4). Chen and colleagues examined the radical scavenging activities of ABTS** in fruit extracts of *Rubia truppeliana* and *R. cordifolia* species. They reported a radical scavenging effect of up to 75% at a concentration of 1.0 mg/mL, although it was lower than that of vitamin C (Chen et al., 2021). In another study, Essaidi and colleagues reported that extracts obtained from RT roots achieved 93% removal at a concentration of 0.8 mg/mL (Essaidi et al., 2017).

Table 4. Trolox equivalents of ABTS** radical scavenging activities of extracts

Extracts	Trolox Equivalent ($\mu\text{g/ mg extract}$)
RTE	66.3
RTM	796
RTK	393
RTP	335

Effects of extracts on AChE and BChE activities

Activity measurements were made at least five different extract concentrations to determine the effects of extracts on AChE and BChE enzyme activities, and % Activity vs. Extract Concentration graphs were plotted. Using graphical equations, IC₅₀ values were calculated for extracts that exhibited inhibitory effects (Kuzu et al., 2018).

Cholinesterase inhibitors accelerate the cholinergic system by slowing or stopping the hydrolysis of ACh, helping to alleviate cognitive deficits. Furthermore, AChE can accelerate amyloid β (A β) accumulation, leading to senile plaque formation. While AChE largely carries out the hydrolysis of ACh, the BChE enzyme also contributes to this function. Both enzymes hydrolyze ACh, thereby inhibiting cholinergic signaling (Çomaklı et al., 2024). According to the results obtained from the study, the IC₅₀ values of the extracts for inhibition of AChE enzyme were 24.03 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ for RTE, 40.29 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ for RTM, and 64.78 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ for RTP. In addition, when the inhibition effect of RTK extract was examined in the concentration range of 0 - 80 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, it was determined that it inhibited the activity by 33.55%. However, since it could not be dropped below 50% activity, the IC₅₀ value for RTK was not calculated (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Activity (%) graphs for RT extracts showing inhibition of the AChE enzyme.

When the effects of the extracts on BChE enzyme activity were examined, it was seen that the extract with the strongest inhibitory effect was RTE with an IC_{50} value of 40.89 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$. While this value was 47.6 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ for RTK extract, it was 58.44 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ for DTM extract. It was determined that the RTP extract had no linear effect on BChE activity in the concentration range of 0-80 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ (Figure 4). The side effects of AChE-inhibiting drugs approved by the FDA and used in treating AD make it important to identify new, plant-derived inhibitors (Alshepy & Kuzu, 2025). Kaya conducted an inhibition study of *L. aureus* extracts on AChE and BChE enzymes and reported that the ethanol extract had the strongest effect. These values were determined as 28.55 mg/mL and 6.78 mg/mL for AChE and BChE, respectively. Content analysis revealed that the main components of this extract were fumaric acid, quinic acid, isoquercitrin, and chlorogenic acid (Kaya, 2025). Compared to our values, the RT ethanol extract appears to have a much stronger effect. Kwon and colleagues also reported that chlorogenic acid inhibited the AChE enzyme in vitro with an IC_{50} value of 98.17 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ (Kwon et al., 2010). Considering that the main components of the RT ethanol extract are fumaric acid, chlorogenic acid, and quinic acid, it can be said that the inhibitory effects are due to these substances.

Figure 4. Activity (%) graphs for RT extracts showing inhibition on the BChE enzyme.

Findings obtained by LC-MS/MS Chromatography

A content analysis of the RT ethanol extract was performed using LC-MS/MS chromatography (Figure 5). The results are presented in Table 5.

Figure 5. Chromatogram of the determination of phenolic compounds by LC-MS/MS chromatography.

Table 5. Amounts of phenolic compounds determined by LC-MS/MS chromatography.

Compound	RT	Response	Concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\text{mg}$ extract)
Quinic Acid	2.375	4890	18.405
Fumaric Acid	3.872	5896	35.113
Gallic Acid	5.422	191	0.0000
Pyrogallol	6.352	4	0.0000
Cyanidin-3-o-glucoside	10.430	174	0.176
Keracyanin Chloride	10.530	0	0.0000
Chlorogenic Acid	10.794	77512	29.258
Catechin	10.884	18	0.0000
Peonidin-3-o-glucoside	10.908	0	0.0000
Epigallocatechin Gallate	11.053	1	0.0000
4-OH-Benzoic Acid	11.182	14249	8.612
Epicatechin	11.233	19	0.0000
Hesperidin	11.574	1624	1.162
Caffeic Acid	11.600	3157	0.0000
Vanillic Acid	11.673	243	4.410
Syringic Acid	11.700	89	0.915
Ellagic Acid	12.087	69	0.0000
Sinapic Acid	12.338	3	0.0000
p-Coumaric Acid	12.355	1386	0.0000
Naringin	12.358	308	0.043
Vitexin	12.360	308	0.0000
Taxifolin	12.420	10	0.0000
Ferulic Acid	12.498	248	0.155
Rosmarinic Acid	12.563	0	0.0000
Vanillin	12.602	0	0.0000
Myricetin	12.825	190	0.0000
Resveratrol	13.164	0	0.0000
Luteolin	13.409	16	0.0000
Quercetin	13.421	5174	0.380
Apigenin	13.990	5	0.0000
Naringenin	14.192	4	0.0000
Isorhamnetin	14.262	62	0.0000

Galangin	15.382	918	0.011
Chrysin	15.557	15	0.0000
Curcumin	16.030	1	0.0000

Accordingly, fumaric acid, chlorogenic acid, quinic acid, and 4-OH-benzoic acid were determined to be the most abundant compounds. A previous study reported that a total of 15 substances, primarily citric acid, ascorbic acid, vanillic acid, epicatechin, and 4-OH-benzoic acid, were detected in the water extract obtained from the plant's roots (Houari et al., 2024). In this study, nine molecules were detected in the ethanolic extract obtained from the leaves and flowers.

CONCLUSION

In this study, extracts were obtained from drug products derived from the leaves and flowers of *Rubia tinctorum* L. using a maceration method with various solvents. In addition to the TPC of the extracts, antioxidant capacity was determined using four different methods. Content analysis was also performed using LC-MS/MS chromatography. The results suggest that the plant may possess antioxidant properties. While previous studies on this plant have generally focused on the root, the properties of the flower and leaf parts were investigated. Furthermore, the extracts were found to have an inhibitory effect on the enzymes AChE and BChE, which are known to affect the cholinergic system and are used as therapeutic targets. In light of these data, it is suggested that plant extracts may exhibit beneficial effects on oxidative stress and could be considered an alternative in treating AD. Furthermore, it would be beneficial to determine the molecules in the extracts that play a role in their effectiveness and the consequences of these effects in vivo.

Acknowledgements

The study was supported by Karabuk University Scientific Research Projects Coordination Unit within the scope of project number KBÜBAP-22-YL-016.

Declaration of interests

The authors declared no conflict of interest.

Author Contributions

1st Author Name-Surname :Data curation; formal analysis; investigation; methodology; writing—original draft.

2st Author Name-Surname :Conceptualization; data curation; formal analysis; funding acquisition; investigation; methodology; project administration; writing— original draft; writing—review and editing.

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